

ImproRisk

“Exposure Assessment in Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA)”

ImproRisk Scientific Report

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1 Summary

Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) is a synthetic, perfluorinated carboxylic acid that has been widely used in industrial applications and consumer products. It is a persistent organic pollutant and a forever chemical, meaning it does not easily break down in the environment or human body.

PFOA was primarily used in the manufacturing of: Non-stick cookware (e.g., Teflon production), Waterproof and stain-resistant coatings (e.g., for textiles, carpets, and upholstery), Firefighting foams (aqueous film-forming foams, AFFF), Food packaging (e.g., grease-resistant paper).

PFOA does not degrade easily and accumulates in human and animal tissues. Its toxicity is linked to kidney and testicular cancer. PFOA exposure is associated with thyroid disease, liver damage, immune system dysfunction, and pregnancy complications. It can affect cholesterol levels and hormone regulation.

In the current report the dietary exposure of the target population is studied using ImproRisk model v.0.6.2. The aim of this risk assessment study was to estimate the dietary intake of Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) for the population in Cyprus, to compare this exposure estimate with the Tolerable Weekly Intake (TWI) of 0.006 µg/kg body weight (b.w.) per week and to calculate the contribution rate of the major food groups to the dietary PFOA exposure.

Mean and 95th percentile dietary PFOA exposure of the Cypriot population was calculated as 0.002 and 0.005 µg/kg b.w. per week, respectively for the MB scenario. It was found that a range of 1.9 to 3.8 % of the whole population was exposed over the TWI value of 0.006µg/Kg b.w. per week, from LB to UB scenario. Much higher exposure was observed for infants, and toddlers due to their lower body weight and their high consumption of milk.

There was a significant difference in PFOA intake between genders and different geographical areas among the population classes.

Milk (40.6%), poultry meat (20.1%) and pig meat (11.1%) were the food categories with the highest contribution to the PFOA intake for the whole population. For infants, milk had the highest contribution (90%) in the exposure.

2 Introduction

Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) is a highly persistent environmental pollutant with significant toxicological effects on humans and animals. Its toxicity is linked to cancer, endocrine disruption, liver damage, immune system dysfunction, and developmental issues.

PFOA toxicity is primarily due to its ability to: (1) Bind to proteins (e.g., albumin) and accumulate in blood and tissues, (2) Disrupt peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors (PPARs), affecting lipid metabolism and liver function, (3) Induce oxidative stress, leading to cell damage and inflammation, and (4) Interfere with hormonal signaling, including thyroid hormone regulation.

Exposure to PFOA is linked to kidney and testicular cancer (based on epidemiological studies). It alters thyroid hormone levels, leading to hypothyroidism or other metabolic disorders, and affects estrogen and androgen activity, potentially impacting fertility. PFOA can cause liver enlargement, increased enzyme levels, and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD).

PFOA has also developmental and reproductive effects (reduces birth weight and delays fetal development, linked to pregnancy complications like preeclampsia, and may affect male reproductive health by reducing sperm quality). It may lower vaccine response and weakens immune defense, and increase susceptibility to infections and autoimmune diseases.

Perfluorooctanoic acid bioaccumulates in animals, leading to reproductive and immune dysfunction in fish, birds, and mammals. It contaminates drinking water, affecting entire populations. It is also persistent in soil and groundwater, making cleanup difficult.

PFOA is a highly toxic "forever chemical" with severe health and environmental consequences. Its persistence and bioaccumulative nature make it a long-term public health challenge. Safer alternatives and water filtration strategies are critical for reducing exposure.

2.1 Background

2.2 Terms of Reference

The aim of this risk assessment study was to estimate the dietary intake of Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) for the population in Cyprus, to compare this exposure estimate with the Tolerable Weekly Intake (TWI) of 0.006 µg/kg body weight (b.w.) per week and to calculate the contribution rate of the major food groups to the dietary PFOA exposure.

3 Data and Methodology

3.1 Occurrence data

3.1.1 Data collection and validation

Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) occurrence data in food were extracted from LIMS for the years 2021-2024, and are shown in Tables 3.1. EFSA's assumption was applied for Low-bound scenario, Middle-bound scenario and Upper-bound scenario. The aggregated occurrence dataset contains occurrence estimates for 45 food items.

3.2 Consumption data

Food consumption data were obtained from the EUMenu project funded by EFSA and the dietary survey was carried out in the years 2014-2018. The consumption data was the result of a survey of 1661 participants (male and female). The survey covered all five cities of Cyprus, rural and urban regions, and also all days of the week and the four seasons. The population classes and the number of participants in each class were: [a] infants: 3-11 months (269), [b] toddlers: 12-35 months (279), [c] other children: 3-9 years (300), [d] adolescents: 10-17 years (274), [e] adults: 18-64 years (275) and [f] elderly: 65-74 years (264). The consumption dataset contains 82921 occasions.

3.3 Food classification

Consumption and occurrence data were both codified according to the FoodEx2 classification system developed by EFSA. At the moment of the generation of the present report the MTX catalogue version 15.3 was applied.

3.4 Methodologies

3.4.1 Chronic dietary exposure

Dietary exposure was assessed at individual level by multiplying the average daily consumption of each food with the corresponding mean occurrence estimated for PFOA summing up the respective intakes throughout the diet and finally dividing the results by the individual's body weight.

3.4.2 Dietary exposure assessment model

Dietary exposure assessment was performed using ImproRisk model version 0.6.2

4 Dietary Exposure Assessment

Table 4.1 presents the substance information.

Table 4.1: Substance information

key	
Chemical Substance	PFOA
Substance Category	Contaminant
Value	0.006 µg/Kg b.w. per week
Type of reference	Tolerable Weekly Intake (TWI)

Table 4.2 presents the exposure statistics.

Table 4.2: Summary exposure statistics of PFOA

Scenario			
key	LB (µg/Kg b.w. per week)	MB (µg/Kg b.w. per week)	UB (µg/Kg b.w. per week)
Min	0	0	0
Max	0.028	0.04	0.052
Mean	0.001	0.002	0.002
95% C.I.	(0.001 - 0.002)	(0.002 - 0.002)	(0.002 - 0.002)
SD	0.002	0.002	0.003
P25	0.001	0.001	0.001
Median	0.001	0.001	0.001
P75	0.002	0.002	0.002
P95	0.004	0.005	0.005
pctOver	1.9%	2.8%	3.8%

* pctOver: Percentage of population above the reference value

Mean and 95th percentile exposure was calculated as 0.002 and 0.005 µg/kg b.w. per week for the MB scenario (Table 4.2). It was found that an average 2.8 % of the whole population was exposed over the TWI value of 0.006 µg/Kg b.w. per week, as also shown in Figures 4.1 and 4.2.

4.1 Distribution of exposure

Probability distribution

Figure 4.1 shows the probability distribution of the exposure.

Figure 4.1: Probability distribution of exposure at the MB scenario

Cumulative distribution

Figure 4.2 shows the cumulative distribution of exposure.

Figure 4.2: Cumulative distribution of exposure at the MB scenario (all population classes)

4.2 Mean Exposure at the MB by Gender

Table 4.3: Summary exposure statistics Gender at MB scenario.

Gender	Min	Max	Mean	95% C.I.	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	pctOver
FEMALE	0	0.0364	0.0016	(0.0015 - 0.0018)	0.0021	0.0007	0.0012	0.0019	0.0045	2.1%
MALE	0	0.0399	0.0019	(0.0017 - 0.002)	0.0022	0.0008	0.0014	0.0021	0.0049	3.6%

Table 4.3 and Figure 4.3 shows that there is a significant difference between the two genders (T test: $t = 2.059$, $p = 0.04$, Effect size: Cohen's $d = 0.1$).

Figure 4.3: Mean Exposure by Gender at MB scenario.

4.3 Mean Exposure at the MB by Area

Table 4.4: Summary exposure statistics by Area at MB scenario.

Area	Min	Max	Mean	95% C.I.	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	pctOver
Ammochostos	0	0.0349	0.0012	(9e-04 - 0.0015)	0.0020	0.0003	0.0008	0.0015	0.0035	1.5%
Larnaka	0	0.0339	0.0017	(0.0015 - 0.002)	0.0025	0.0008	0.0012	0.0017	0.0045	3.8%
Lefkosia	0	0.0334	0.0019	(0.0017 - 0.002)	0.0023	0.0007	0.0013	0.0021	0.0052	3.3%
Lemesos	0	0.0399	0.0018	(0.0016 - 0.002)	0.0021	0.0008	0.0014	0.0021	0.0046	2.7%
Pafos	0	0.0360	0.0016	(0.0014 - 0.0019)	0.0015	0.0007	0.0014	0.0023	0.0033	1%

Table 4.4 and Figure 4.4 shows that there is no significant difference (when applying parametric statistical tests) between the five areas of the dietary survey in Cyprus.

Figure 4.4: Mean Exposure by Area at MB scenario.

4.4 Mean Exposure at the MB by Population Class

Table 4.5: Summary exposure statistics by Population Class at MB scenario.

Population class	Min	Max	Mean	95% C.I.	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	pctOver
Adolescents	0.0000	0.0072	0.0021	(0.002 - 0.0023)	0.0012	0.0013	0.0020	0.0028	0.0043	0.8%
Adults	0.0000	0.0077	0.0013	(0.0012 - 0.0014)	0.0009	0.0007	0.0011	0.0017	0.0030	0.4%
Elderly	0.0000	0.0032	0.0009	(8e-04 - 0.001)	0.0006	0.0005	0.0009	0.0013	0.0021	0%
Infants	0.0000	0.0399	0.0093	(0.0078 - 0.0108)	0.0122	0.0000	0.0024	0.0170	0.0317	37.6%
Other children	0.0004	0.0152	0.0041	(0.0038 - 0.0044)	0.0024	0.0024	0.0036	0.0053	0.0088	17.6%
Toddlers	0.0000	0.0207	0.0042	(0.0038 - 0.0047)	0.0039	0.0015	0.0028	0.0061	0.0128	25.5%

Figure 4.5: Mean Exposure by Population Class at MB scenario.

In Table 4.5 and Figure 4.5 the exposure of each population class is shown. It was found that infant had the highest mean exposure, followed by toddlers and other children. The lower body weight of these population classes is a reason for the higher exposure. Toddlers and other children showed two- to three-times higher exposure than adolescents and adults. On the other hand, infants showed five-times higher exposure than adolescents and ten times higher exposure than adults. Furthermore, 37.6% of infants, 25.5% of toddlers and 17.6% of other children were exceeding the TWI for PFOA intake. Investigating the consumption data, it was observed that infants and toddlers were mostly exposed due to their high consumption of milk. In the case of infants, where their main diet is human milk (around 1-liter per day), because of the absence of occurrence data in human milk the exposure calculation was performed using the concentration levels of milk. Literature research showed that mean concentration values of PFOA in breast milk were similar with those of milk used in this study.

4.5 Mean Exposure at the MB scenario by [Area and Population Class]

Figure 4.6 illustrates the mean exposure to PFOA by population class and geographical area. It was found that there is a significant difference between the geographical areas in all population classes. In all areas the highest exposure was observed for infants.

4.6 Contributions of different food groups to the dietary exposure

The contribution of each main food group to the total PFOA exposure for the whole population is shown in Figure 4.7. Milk (41.3%), pig meat (19.2%), and poultry meat (18.7%) were the food categories with the highest contribution to the PFOA intake. Several fish species consumed in Cyprus presented an average of 4.5% contribution to the total exposure. Pig and poultry meat presented similar concentration levels and consumption rate. Although bovine meat had higher concentration levels showed less contribution to the total exposure due to the much lower consumption rate in Cyprus. In general, similar contribution profile was observed in all population classes with the exception of infants where milk had the highest contribution (88%) in PFOA exposure. Milk has the highest contribution especially in population classes with low body weight, because it is a food that is consumed in large amounts. The extreme high percentage in infants is due to the fact that milk is their main diet, consuming around 1-liter human milk per day.

Figure 4.6 shows the contribution of food items at FoodEx Level 4

Figure 4.6: Contribution to the PFOA Total Exposure MB.

Table 4.6 shows the contribution of food items at FoodEx Level 4

Table 4.6: Contribution to the PFOA Total Exposure (MB). Food items at FoodEx2 Level 4 with greater than 1% contribution

Food category	Food level	Population class	Contribution to Total exposure
Other milks	4	Infants	87.39%
Cattle milk	4	Other children	57.26%
Cattle milk	4	Adolescents	48.12%
Cattle milk	4	Toddlers	42.56%
Cattle milk	4	Elderly	41.61%
Cattle milk	4	ALL	41.28%
Cattle milk	4	Adults	37.81%
Pig fresh meat	4	Adults	27.53%
Pig fresh meat	4	Elderly	25.06%
Poultry fresh meat (muscle meat)	4	Toddlers	21.98%
Poultry fresh meat (muscle meat)	4	Adults	20.96%
Pig fresh meat	4	Adolescents	20.36%
Pig fresh meat	4	ALL	19.19%
Poultry fresh meat (muscle meat)	4	ALL	18.69%
Poultry fresh meat (muscle meat)	4	Adolescents	18.03%
Poultry fresh meat (muscle meat)	4	Other children	18.02%
Poultry fresh meat (muscle meat)	4	Elderly	16.98%
Pig fresh meat	4	Other children	11.08%
Other milks	4	Toddlers	10.07%
Pig fresh meat	4	Toddlers	8.48%
Other milks	4	ALL	7.46%
Poultry fresh meat (muscle meat)	4	Infants	6.18%

Food category	Food level	Population class	Contribution to Total exposure
Bovine fresh meat	4	Toddlers	5.40%
Bovine fresh meat	4	Infants	4.68%
Bovine fresh meat	4	Adolescents	3.87%
Bovine fresh meat	4	Elderly	3.75%
Salmons, trouts, smelts	4	Adults	3.75%
Bovine fresh meat	4	ALL	3.48%
Bovine fresh meat	4	Adults	3.27%
Flavoured milks	4	Other children	3.11%
Goat milk	4	Toddlers	2.91%
Bovine fresh meat	4	Other children	2.69%
Salmons, trouts, smelts	4	ALL	2.45%
Miscellaneous coastal marine fishes	4	Elderly	2.26%
Flavoured milks	4	Adolescents	2.24%
Hen eggs	4	Toddlers	2.16%
Salmons, trouts, smelts	4	Elderly	2.10%
Sheep fresh meat	4	Elderly	2.02%
Hen eggs	4	Adults	1.79%
Goat milk	4	Other children	1.78%
Miscellaneous coastal marine fishes	4	Adults	1.69%
Hen eggs	4	ALL	1.57%
Hen eggs	4	Adolescents	1.55%
Salmons, trouts, smelts	4	Toddlers	1.52%
Hen eggs	4	Other children	1.49%
Salmons, trouts, smelts	4	Adolescents	1.47%
Salmons, trouts, smelts	4	Other children	1.46%

Food category	Food level	Population class	Contribution to Total exposure
Hen eggs	4	Elderly	1.44%
Miscellaneous coastal marine fishes	4	ALL	1.36%
Miscellaneous coastal marine fishes	4	Toddlers	1.28%
Flavoured milks	4	Toddlers	1.27%
Miscellaneous coastal marine fishes	4	Other children	1.25%
Flavoured milks	4	ALL	1.19%
Sheep fresh meat	4	Adolescents	1.11%
Canned-tinned meat	4	Elderly	1.02%

5 Uncertainties

The evaluation of the uncertainties in the exposure assessment of PFOA has been performed following the guidance of the Opinion of the Scientific Committee related to Uncertainties in Dietary Exposure Assessment. Table 5.1 presents a summary of uncertainties, highlighting the main sources of uncertainty and providing an estimate whether each source of uncertainty is likely to lead to an over- or under-estimation of the calculated dietary exposure.

Table 5.1: Summary of qualitative evaluation of the impact of uncertainties on the dietary exposure.

Sources of uncertainty	Direction ¹
Different time frame between concentration data and consumption data	+/-
Long-term (chronic) exposure assessed from few days of consumption	+
Measurement error in amounts of food consumed	+/-
Measurement error in individual body weights	+/-
Assumptions taken into account for the aggregation of occurrence data	+/-
Use of the substitution method for non-detects	+/-
Use of weight coefficients for non-representativeness of the population	+/-
Level up approach matching in the FoodEx2 exposure hierarchy for the calculation of the exposure	+

¹+ = uncertainty with potential to cause over-estimation of exposure; - = uncertainty with potential to cause under-estimation of exposure

A number of uncertainties can be identified regarding the selection of parameters, such as PFOA concentration levels in foodstuffs and consumption data.

The uncertainty related to the representativeness of the occurrence data for certain food commodities with respect to the number of samples is taken into account. Given the fact that the analytical results were generated in an accredited laboratory, this adds only slightly to the uncertainty of the analytical results.

Some potentially important extrapolation uncertainties arise since an individual survey of food consumption is used to estimate dietary exposure over a timescale longer than the survey duration. Remaining uncertainties relate to the measurement error in amounts of consumed foodstuffs and individual body weights.

In ImproRisk occurrence and consumption data matching for the calculation of the exposure is performed based on a level up approach matching in the FoodEx2 exposure hierarchy, which may lead to overestimation of the exposure.

Furthermore, several assumptions taken into account in the preparation of the occurrence data may lead to some uncertainties.

6 Conclusions

Mean and 95th percentile dietary PFOA exposure of the Cypriot population was calculated as 0.002 and 0.005 µg/kg b.w. per week, respectively for the MB scenario. It was found that a range of 1.9 to 3.8 % of the whole population was exposed over the TWI value of 0.006µg/Kg b.w. per week, from LB to UB scenario. Much higher exposure was observed for infants, and toddlers due to their lower body weight and their high consumption of milk.

There was a significant difference in PFOA intake between genders and different geographical areas among the population classes.

Milk (40.6%), poultry meat (20.1%) and pig meat (11.1%) were the food categories with the highest contribution to the PFOA intake for the whole population. For infants, milk had the highest contribution (90%) in the exposure.

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8 Abbreviations

Table 8.1: Abbreviations

Key	Description
BMDL	Benchmark dose lower limit (lower bound of benchmark dose interval)
b.w.	Body weight
LB	Lower bound
LOD	Limit of detection
MB	Middle bound
MoE	Margin of exposure
SD	Standard deviation
P25	25th percentile
P75	75th percentile
P95	95th percentile
UB	Upper bound
wcoeff	Weight coefficient

9 Appendices